

Efficient degradation of Bismarck brown by the halotolerant *Virgibacillus dokdonensis* VIT P14

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Abstract : Biodegradation is defined as the process in which microorganisms are exploited for their capacity to degrade the hazardous compounds. Especially, the degradation of the dyes by the microbes has attained great interest due to low cost, simple process and maintenance conditions. Keeping this in mind, we have exploited the novel organism *Virgibacillus dokdonensis* VIT P14, isolated from Kumta coast (Karnataka), for degrading the azo dye Bismarck brown. The maximum degradation of about 91.2% was obtained in the media containing 1 mg of the dye along with the loopful of inoculum grown for 24 h in the shaking condition. Effect of chemical and physical parameters such as pH, temperature, dye concentration, shaking and static conditions, sodium chloride concentration, glucose concentration, urea concentration were also studied in detail with respect to bacterial growth in the presence of the azo dye. The results revealed significant parameters that contributed to efficient dye degradation. The ability of the organism to grow under saline conditions and in the presence of the azodye makes it a possible candidate for bioremediation of textile waste water.

Keywords : Biodegradation, bio-sorption, azodyes, decolorization.

Introduction

Synthetic dyes released from the textile and paper industries are found to be generally toxic. One such example of these synthetic dyes is the azo dye (e.g. monoazo, diazo, triazo, and polyazo). Azo dyes are the largest class of organic colorants and possess the azo group of two nitrogen atoms (N=N) that connects the aromatic ring compounds. Azo dyes may be direct, acid, or basic. Direct dyes contain relatively large molecules with higher affinity especially towards fibers¹. Biological techniques for the treatment such as bacterial and fungal bio-sorption and biodegradation in the aerobic or anaerobic/aerobic treatment processes have been practiced since long time². Synthetic dyes have a larger application in the fields of food, pharmaceutical, textile, cosmetic and paper industries³. Azo dyes are the largest group of dyes employed in the industry⁴ and represent more than half of the annual production⁵. During the dyeing processes, it has been found and estimated that about 10% of the dye stuff used do not bind themselves to the fibers and is therefore released directly into the sewage treatment systems or the environment⁶.

Textile industries produce the larger amount of the colored dye effluents that are not only toxic but also found

to be non-biodegradable⁷⁻⁹. However, these techniques are found to be non-destructive^{10,11}. Hence, azo dyes create lot of problem mainly due to their product entry into the environmental phases¹². In fact, the effluent streams that are released from the textile plants must be treated with the purpose of removing the toxic or carcinogenic dye residues and their by-products, whereas most government regulations requires an effective effluent decolorization¹³⁻¹⁵. Studies have shown that certain bacteria are capable of degrading azo dye¹⁶⁻¹⁸. On considering the above literature, the novel organism capable of depleting the azodye compounds has been exploited and optimized with various parameters.

Experimental

The organism isolation and authentication was already reported in the previous works related to the organism. The organism was tested for its decolorization efficiency by allowing their growth in the nutrient agar plate containing the dye (1 mg/100 ml). The formation of the zone around the colonies was evaluated and then further studies were carried out. Dye stock (1 mg/100 ml) of Bismarck brown was used throughout the experiment. The organisms and the dye solution maintained in vari-

ous parameters such as different pH, temperature, dye, sodium chloride, urea, glucose, static and shearing were also optimized in the desired growth period of 24 h at the incubator. The organism treated dye solutions of about 5 ml was centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 15 min in order to separate the bacterial biomass and the resulting supernatant was measured for its absorbance using UV-Visible spectroscopy at 442 nm. The absorbance of the dye before and after the treatment was recorded and the decolorization percentage was calculated by using the equation :

$$\% \text{Decolorization} = \frac{[\text{Initial absorbance} - \text{final absorbance}]}{\text{Initial absorbance}} \times 100$$

Results and discussion

In the present study, the organism was optimized for its decolorization efficiency at various parameters. One among them is the sodium chloride concentration tested in the range from 0.01 mg, 0.1 mg, 1, 2 to 3 mg per experimental setup containing 10 ml of the culture grown in the nutrient media along with known dye concentration. The decolorization percentage was found to increase upon increasing the sodium chloride concentration which shows the halo tolerant potential of the culture besides dye degradation as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Effect of sodium chloride on the degradation of Bismarck brown.

The effect of urea and glucose at the same concentrations also promoted the decolorization frequency as shown in Figs. 2 and 3. But, the increase in the dye concentration from 1 to 6 mg/100 ml was found to decrease the decolorization frequency as shown in Fig. 4.

pH and temperature are the major microenvironment required by the organism for its optimal growth. Hence,

Fig. 2. Effect of urea concentration on the degradation of Bismarck brown.

Fig. 3. Effect of glucose concentration on the degradation of Bismarck brown.

Fig. 4. Effect of dye concentration on the degradation of Bismarck brown.

the effect of pH and temperature on the degradation potential was evaluated (Figs. 5 and 6). The dye degradation was found to be maximum at the pH of 5 and temperature of 50 °C.

Finally, the effect of shearing and static condition on the degradation potential of the dyes were also evaluated and was found that the shearing promotes the degradation to about 15% on comparison with the static condition (Fig. 7).

Fig. 5. Effect of pH on the degradation of Bismarck brown.

Fig. 6. Effect of temperature on the degradation of Bismarck brown.

Fig. 7. Effect of reaction condition on the degradation of Bismarck brown.

Conclusion

Degradation of dyes using the biological organisms has been the topic of interest in the present days due to the cost and eco-friendly nature. Hence, the organism capable of degrading the azodyes were exploited and reported for their degradation nature. Various conditions favoring the maximum degradation of the dyes were done and found to show positive enhancement. The organism could be employed at the industrial level for the degrada-

tion of the dye containing waste water effluents in order to prevent the environmental pollution.

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